

Exploring the Potential of Ancient Jain Heritage Tourism in Bankura District: A Geospatial Approach

Souradeep Das¹, Dr. Anupam Jash², Dr. Subrata Pan³

Abstract:

The concept of Jainism is thrived into the vent of Ancient India as well as in the history of ancient Bengal. Though the actual time about the establishment of the Jain ideology in Bengal is unknown to us but ancient texts and scripts indicates about the authenticity. There is no doubt that the *Tirthankaras* visited this land in different historical time period which helped to flourish this significant ideology. One can observe the importance of ‘Radh Pradesh’ or modern Western part of West Bengal including Bankura, Purulia, Birbhum, Burdwan, and Midnapore in the life of respective *Tirthankaras*. Nowadays numerous excavated Jain Idols, icons, ancient stone temples with various styles like *deula*, *shikara*, votive stupas from different sites bears the evidence of Jainism in Bankura district. These sites remain largely unexplored in the tourism domain. This study aims to analyze the potentiality of Jain heritage tourism by using several geospatial techniques which is a unique approach in such type of study. Location map of those sites or spatial distributions, circuit maps in two districts with shortest path, isochrone maps, service area delineation by using buffer analysis, iconography analysis, density of sites in each districts and analysis of the accessibility and connectivity between those sites will help the tourists and academicians to measure the potentiality of such type of tourism. Apart from these techniques, the study also tried to find the conservation status of those sites by Government Archaeological Department or by local communities. By using Thematic mapping, the conservation status has also been displayed. By connecting geospatial tools with historical insights, the study offers strategic recommendations for sustainable tourism practices and heritage conservation in those sites as these sites are important from Tourism as well as archaeological and geographical point of view.

Keywords: *Jainism, Geospatial Analysis, Sustainable Tourism, Archaeology, Heritage Tourism*

¹UG Student, Department of Geography, Bankura Christian College

²Associate Professor, Department of Philosophy, Bankura Christian College

³Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bankura Christian College

Introduction:

Jainism is considered as one of the oldest established religions in the land of ancient India. The western part of west Bengal in India also hosted this religion as a new ideology. The story about the establishment was also became a legend to the rural people of this region. Though this peaceful ideology have removed almost from this region but several evidence bearing significant archaeological sites like temples, idols or icons showing the remarkable legacy. These scattered or fragmented sculptures across Bankura district not only represent the ancient achievements of Jainism throughout the area but also holds the potentiality of heritage or pilgrimage tourism which is an important subgroup or branch of tourism. The present study aims to observe and analyze the prospect of those sites as a Jain heritage tourism sites through Geographical Information System (GIS) which will superimpose the information technology over the authentic representations of Jain history.

Analytical Framework:

Review of Literature:

‘Tourism’ refers to the temporary travel of people to destinations(Dilek & Dilek, 2018) away from their usual surroundings for several purposes like leisure, amusement, business(Noroozi, 2020) or enjoying some interesting objects or phenomena or charming scenery etc. (Netto, 2009). It involves socio-cultural and economic activities(Noroozi, 2020) of the visitors in those particular sites. The term ‘Tourism’ is like a tree or an umbrella which gives shelter several other branches or streams like Dark Tourism(Seaton, 1996; Stone, 2006), Heritage Tourism(Bhowmik, 2021; Poria et al., 2003), Pilgrimage Tourism(Kreiner, 2020; Galzacorta et al., 2016)etc. The present study deals with the concept of Heritage Tourism in the backdrop of the spatial distribution of Jainism in Bankura district . Here the question arises that, how this pure ideology came into this land? And why the visitorschoose to visit these sites containing remains of Jainism as a tourist place in 21st century? The advent of Jainism in ‘Radha’ area or ‘Paniyabhumi’ or present western part of West Bengal state of India started from the footfall of Lord Mahavira (The 24th Tirthankara in Jainism) in this land. Verses in Several ancient Jain texts like *Ācārāṅga Sutra*, *Bhagavati Sutra*, *Kalpa Sutra*, *Kathakosha* and *Divyavadana* shows the proof about the emergence of Lord Mahavira in this place. ‘Chandimangal’ of Kavikankan Mukundaram Chakravarti also contains evidences. The *Avasyak Curni* shows the reason behind the arrival of this legend which was to ‘shed the Karmas’(Jash, 2022). Verses of *Ācārāṅga*

Sutra (Muni) i.e. 294, 295, 296, 297, 298, 299, 300, 301, 302, 303, 304, 305 and 306 respectively shows the difficulties that Lord *Mahavira* and *Sramanas* faced during the travel in this land like the residents of this land attacked and delivered ‘thorn-like’ words to him. According to R.C.Majumdar (1971), “It was difficult to travel in Ladha”. Wild dogs attacked the Lord and he faced extreme adversities like scorching hot and cool weather and stinging of several insects in this area. The *Ācārāṅga Sutra*, *Bhagavati Sutra*, *Avashyaka Curni*, *Acaranga Curni* depicts a pen-picture about the entry of ‘Jaina way of Life’ at Bengal (Jash, 2022). Archaeological written evidences like Hatigumpha inscription of Kalinga King Kharvela, Mathura Inscription and Paharpur Copper-plate in Bangladesh shows the influence of Jainism in Bengal during Nanda, Kushana and Gupta rule respectively. He resided here about 6 years and gradually he won the heart of people (Chakrabarty, 2018) by his determinations and will power. The *Kalpa Sutra* indicates that Lord Mahavira visited the ‘*Paniyabhumi*’ and spent a rainy season (Chattopadhyaya, 1953). Famous Kalinga King ‘Gajapati’ Anantavarman Chodaganga Deva, was responsible for constructing many Jain stone temples in Bankura and Purulia district for the ‘Digambara’ sector during 11th to 12th century (Khan & Sinha, 2024). Several reports or researches of foreign scholars like O’ Malley (1910), Hunter (1877), Ball (1869), Marriott, Coupland, Dalton (1966) as well as many Indian Scholars like Majumdar (2017) has contributed in the recording of regional as well as spatial distribution of Jain archaeological sites in these two districts. The present study delves into the use of sophisticated Geospatial techniques or especially Geographic Information Technology in promotion of Jain archaeological sites as tourists spot and managing those sites (Lepetiuk et al., 2023) for the development of tourism industry and transportation. In last 10 to 15 years, many works have been done by using this techniques to promote several heritage sites in different countries like Analysis of Hotel Locations near sites (Amanda & Widaningrum, 2021), Isochrones Mapping for measuring travel time and distance (Lepetiuk et al., 2023), Route Planning and classifications of targeted sites (Yang, 2014; Lepetiuk V. B., 2020), observing the accessibility and connectivity of the sites using network analysis by GIS (Nagne & Gawali, 2013), Tourism Attractiveness Analysis of regions (Lepetiuk V. B., 2020), Best Route Optimizations (Derek & Sikora, 2019), Web-Mapping systems (Supak et al., 2014) etc. Very few studies have been done in India to explore this vast tracts of Bengal. A significant work by Shrinwantu Raha and Shasanka Kumar Gayen (2022) on Tourism potentiality in Bankura district was carried out recently. Further studies are required in these two districts for heritage management which will not only flourish the Jain sector but also the other branches of tourism.

Objectives of the Study:

Culture and Heritage Tourism indicates economy as a weapon of development (Rosenfeld, 2008) by which the visitors are attracted by the scenic representation of the glorious past of a particular community or region through historical or archaeological fragments or remains of past and present cultural landscape (Sauer, 1963) in a particular region which also includes language, tradition, beliefs or way of life of those settled community. Now in the case of Jainism, the potentiality of the heritage sites in two districts associated with the ideology of Jainism are remain unexplored and totally neglected by the state and central government of India, and there is a lack of interest of the researchers or scholars towards the study of this type of tourism. To address and minimize the gap, this study indicates some specific objectives which are:

1. To identify the Jain Sites and to locate those in the study area with an emphasis on exploring historical and archaeological significance of the sites.
2. To explore the pilgrimage and heritage tourism potential in line with the established tourist destination.
3. Planning for Sustainable Jain Pilgrimage and Heritage Tourism using Geospatial Technology.
4. To provide suggestions for conservation of Jain Heritage Sites and to develop tourism infrastructure for potential visitors.

Overview of the Study Area with Historical Context from Jain Literature:

The vast western undulating tract or plateau area of West Bengal state include Bankura district which was part of the 'Radha' or 'Ladha' area in the entire ancient historical time period which had also two subdivisions i.e. *Vajjabhumi* and *Subbhabhumi* (Mazumdar, 1984) which were blessed by the holy traces of Lord Mahavira's feet. Here famous historian Ramesh Chandra Majumdar in his book 'History of Ancient Bengal' stated the 'Ladha' area as a 'Pathless Country' or 'Duchchara' (Majumdar, 1971) where the behavior of the native people was rude and where travelling was difficult. Here Jinadasa Gani indicates 'Radha' as 'Non-Aryan Country'. This region have a mixture of unique plateau and plane landscape. Presently, The Bankura district shares its administrative boundary with Purulia, both Purba and Paschim Burdwan, Paschim Medinipur, Hooghly districts The region enjoys scorching hot summer, moderate monsoon and cool winter. The key tourist hub are Susunia, Mukutmanipur,

Biharinath, Bishnupur in Bankura. The study area is connected by several state and national highways and by South Eastern Railway. Kolkata and Durgapur airports are nearby airports. With proper plan, investment and infrastructural development this area can be an international hub of Cultural heritage and eco-tourism.

Figure 1. Geographical Location of the study area (Source. Prepared by the Authors)

Data Source and Methodology:

The present study use both primary and secondary data to analyze and manage the sites. The primary data collection was conducted by GPS survey. The secondary information about those sites were acquired from bulletin, district gazetteers, archaeological survey report of both Archaeological Survey of India and State Archaeological department of West Bengal, research papers, books, ancient Jain texts etc. The Google Earth Pro software has been used to identify the Jain archaeological sites which are distributed in the remote villages, agricultural fields and forests of Bankura. The spatial coordinates of those places were acquired from that software by adding the place mark. After that the coordinates were recorded in MS Excel software and later it was converted into .CSV file. The CSV file was imported into QGIS software (version: 3.34.4) for several spatial analysis. The road network data and Shape file was acquired from mainly OSM (Open Street Maps) plugin of QGIS software (version: 3.34.4). The other village

level road network data was acquired from PMGSY (Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojna) National GIS website by which the accessibility of those tourist sites were estimated. Besides these, the conservation status, infrastructure related tourist facilities of those heritage sites were carried out by personal observation.

Figure 2: Identification and Coordinate Acquisition of Bahulara Jain Heritage Site in Google Earth Pro

Results and Discussions:

With the data collected from different sources, review of various literature on Jain tourism sites and their antiquities, several types of geospatial analysis were undertaken to reach following results and discussions on the potential Jain pilgrimage and Heritage Tourism in Bankura district of west Bengal which have been performed by using the locational and road network data. The types are:

1. Identification of Jain Tourism sites.
2. Geographical Distribution of Jain Heritage Tourism Sites.
3. Preparation of Creating Shortest Route Jain Tourism Circuit.
4. Isochrones Mapping.
5. Tourist Facilities Proximity Delineation using Buffer Analysis
6. Road Network Density Analysis.
7. Classification of Sites from Archaeological Context.

1. Identification of Jain Heritage Sites:

Several types of fragments or archaeological remains associated with Jainism have been unearthed, excavated or founded from the different parts in the study area. Mainly Stone temple remains, Jain icons, Caumukhas, Votive stupas, Images, fragmented idols of *Tirthankaras* and *Yakshinis* comes under the findings. The present study shows the graphical representation and block wise distribution of those sites in two districts thematically by which the researchers, visitors or the Jain Pilgrims can take a glimpse of those sites without studying the texts. It will help to promote the tourism.

Figure 3. Identification of Jain Heritage Sites in study area (Source. Prepared by the Authors based on Literature and Field Survey)

2. Geographical Distributions of Jain Heritage Sites:

This map shows the number of sites in each block using categorized colour. The shades of each color represents the frequency. Visitors or researchers can gain a simple idea about the block-wise distribution of the heritage sites. On the basis of this categorization, the government can observe which block needs the tourist facilities, conservation efforts, better road accessibility and better infrastructure.

Figure 4: Distribution of Jain Heritage Sites (Source: Prepared by the Authors based on Literature and Field Survey)

3. Preparation of Jain Tourism Circuits:

This analysis is significant from the tourism and transportation point of view. In the present study, the proposed Jain heritage tourism circuits have been prepared by using ORS (Open Route Service) tools of QGIS software (version: 3.34.4). The route of this circuit follows the shortest distance between the sites. This analysis involves two types of routes i.e. Primary and Secondary route. As the main tourist hubs are Bishnupur, Mukutmanipur and Susunia, the secondary shortest path circuits involves the Jain heritage sites which are distributed near these primary tourist hubs. In this way, six circuits have been proposed in the study area. These circuits will guide the visitors for visiting Jain Tourism sites to any nearby important tourist hub. The local tour operator may also conduct a day trip to all these unexplored Jain sites for fulfilling and satisfying tourism experience in the study area by blending nature and cultural tourism. This will definitely contribute to rural economy of the area. The entry and exit route have also been indicated to the tourists by using these maps. A summary table have also been prepared to show the sites on the basis of the shortest path circle, the types of antiquities which are found in these places.

Table 1. Entry and Exit Routes to the Jain Heritage Sites. (Prepared by the Authors)

District	Entry Route	Route Name	Exit Route	Route Name
Bankura	By Road:	State	By Road:	State Highway 8
	Arambagh-Kotulpur	Highway 2	Saltora-Raghunathpur	
	By Railway:	Howrah-Ranchi	By Railway:	Howrah- Ranchi
	Bishnupur Junction	railway	Jhatipahari station	Railway

Table 2. Summary of Jain Heritage Tourism sites with Associated Shortest Route Circle in Bankura District (Source: Prepared by the Authors Based on Field Survey)

Jain Tourism Circuits	Jain Sites Under The Shortest Route Circle	Jain Antiquities
Bishnupur Circuits	Acharya Jogeshchandra Vidyandihi Purakriti Vaban, Bishnupur	Jain Choumukha, Jaina Tirthankara idol excavated from different village ponds in Bankura District
	Kumbhasthal	Lord Mahavira in Dhyana Pose
	Salda	Muni Subrata Swami idol remains As Bhairab below Tetul Tree, Lord Santinathnath
	Gokulnagar	Lord Neminath
	Rahagram	Tirthankar idol Remains
	Dhara	Jaina Choumukha
	Siromonipur	Lord Risabhnath,
	Benepara	Jaina Yakshini
	Indas Bankura Roy dalan	Jaina Ayagpatta
	Sonamukhi	Lord Risabhnath (Between Swarnamayee and Mahisasurmardini idol)
	Sonatapol	Jaina Yakshini
	Bahulara	Lord Parshwanath
	Ajodhya	Lord Risabhnath, Jain Deul (Makra

		stone
	Dharapat	Lord Risabhath, Lord Parshwanath, Lord Santinath, Jaina Choumukha
Mukutmanipur Circuit	Gorabari	Lord Santinath
	Ambikanagar	Ambika, Lord Risabhath, Amlak sila, Lord Santinath,
	Pareshnath	Lord Parshwanath, Devi Ambika, Lord Parshwanath
	Kechanda	Goddess Ambika
	Satpatta Shiva Sitala Temple	Devi Ambika, Lord Parshwanath
	Laupara Khandarani Goram Than	Jaina Tirthnkara,
	Dumurtore Kalmadan Temple	Lord Parshwanath
	Jarishya	Jaina Yakshini
	Simlapal Rajbari Balaram Temple	Lord Mahavira, Devi Ambika, Lord Neminath, Lord Santinath
	Ganra	Jaina Tirthnkara
	Lakhmisagar Alakdhara	Lord Mahavira
	Shyampur Rukmini Devasthan	Lord Risabhath
	Harmasra Jain Temple	Jain Temple Sikhar Deul
	Gobindapur	Broken Jaina Deul, Amlak sila
	Jiarda	Lord Parshwanath
	Bheduasole	Broken Jaina Deul, kalas
	Panch Pukuria	Lord Parshwanath, Amlak Sila
	Junbedia	Lord Mahavira
	BaraJorda	Lord Parshwanath
Tungi	Lord Ajitnath, Jaina Yakshini	
Gopalpur	Lord Parshwanath	
Susunia Circit	Bharatpur	Yakshini at Basantakumari temple at Palashjhor
	Chatna Basuli Temple	Jaina Ayagpatta, Amlak sila
	Molbana	Lord Parshwanath, Jain Choumukha

	Bikna	Dwarpala
	Biharjuriya	Tirthankar idol
	Harekrishnapur	Jain Choumukha
	Pakhanna	Trthankar Mahavira
	Thumkora	Tirthankar idol
	Bhului	Trthankar idol
	Biharinath Hill	Lord Parshwanath

	Tiluri	Lord Chandraprabha, Yaksha-yakshini
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Figure 5. Jain Tourism Circuits of Bankura District.

4. Isochrones Mapping for assessment of shortest travel time from hub to the sites:

The next significant analysis that the present study uses is 'Isochrones Travel Time Mapping'. Travel time assessment is also an important observation besides the accessibility, transportation infrastructure and condition. Simply, in transport studies, an isochrone map is used to connect those point to which the traversing time is same (Desai, 2008). These are also known as 'iso-accessibility lines' (Lepetiuk et al., 2023). Cartographer Francis Galton is

known as the father of this mapping technique as he created ‘Isochronic Passage Charts’ (Galton, 1881) for the travelers and sailors of London. In this study, the authors have prepared 6 isochrone maps in two respective districts. To observe the travel time from the main tourism hub to the Jain Heritage Tourism sites, simplified colored isochrones have been constructed by using Open Route Service (ORS) Routing Tool Plugin of QGIS (Version: 3.34.4). The Configuration of the isochrones largely depends on existing road network. The visitors will be able to assess the time required to travel each circuit.

4.1 Isochrones in Bankura District:

Figure 7. Susunia Circuit Isochrones Map (Source. Prepared by the Authors)

Figure 8. Bishnupur Circuit Isochrone Map (Source. Prepared by the Authors)

Figure 9. Mukutmanipur Circuit Isochrones Map (Source. Prepared by the Authors)

5. Proximity Delineation using Buffer Analysis:

Besides shortest travel time assessments, visitor's satisfaction can be enhanced by indicating them about the other facilities distributed around the sites. Being a socio-economic activity, the quality enhancement of visitor's experience and safety are the main goal in the sustainable tourism activity. The present study has taken Bahulara Jain heritage site of Bankura district to show an example for such type of observations. As the site (locally known as mainly Siddheswar temple) is situated in a remote village at Onda CD block in Bankura district, the accessibility to nearby accommodations, Rail Stations, ATM, Petrol Pump, Police Station, and Block Hospitals has also been demarcated by using 5 rings with 5km interval. The total analysis has been performed using Multi-ring buffer tool Plugin of QGIS software (Version: 3.34.4). The location of the hotels, Stations and other facility sites have been imported to the software canvas by using CSV file. This type of mapping can be done with all Jain sites.

Figure 13. Proximity Analysis of Bahulara Temple (Source. Prepared by the Author)

6. Connectivity Estimation of Sites by Road Network Density Analysis:

For the development and strategy building for making sustainable tourism activities, road accessibility is important as transportation is a significant component for enhancing the tourism potentiality of an archaeological or heritage site particularly located in remote rural areas (Dascălu et al., 2024). These sites have the potentials to make a micro-economy in the surrounding area for which the sites has to depend upon the transportation quality. As a developing country, the rural road networks in India needs improvement. In the present study, the block wise density of rural road network has been calculated by intersection, dissolving and Attribute Calculation and Attribute joining in QGIS software (version: 3.34.4). There are several suitable ways to measure the connectivity are Alpha, Beta, and Gama Index and to measure the accessibility are Cyclomatic Number, Shimbel index etc. The Road density is the easiest way to represent degree of connectivity and accessibility between the sites and can be estimated by:

$$RD = \frac{\sum L}{A}$$

Where, RD = Road Density (km / km²)

ΣL = Total Length of Roads in a region / block (in km) and,

A= The Area of the region / block (in km^2)

The road network shape-file has been imported from PMGSY National GIS website. As the Jain sites are majorly located in the rural areas so village level data is more important. After intersecting, length measurement and dissolving the data, the attribute table has joined with the attribute table of study area shape-file. After calculation, the values are classified into 5 classes and then the shaded graduated colour is used for better representation. Deep colour region indicates high road density and vice versa. After that, the location of Jain heritage sites has been superimposed over the choropleth map. Those sites, which are located in the blocks having high road density are most accessible and vice versa. Management of tourism, heritage conservation and route planning actions are totally correlated with the degree of density of road network in each block.

Figure 14. Block-wise Rural Road Network Density in Bankura District with Superimposed Jain Heritage Sites (Source. Prepared by the Authors)

7. Classification of Jain Heritage Sites:

The Jain Heritage sites of Bankura district represents various types of archaeological materials like Stone Temples, Icons, Votive Stupas, Amlak Sila, Kalas, Fragmented Idols of

Tirthankaras and *Yakshinis*, Caumukhas etc. which needs concerted conservation and restorations strategies. Some Jain stone temples like Sonatapal, Bahulara, Deulbhira in Bankura are in better condition as they are protected by Archaeological Survey of India and other non-governmental groups and NGOs but the other sites are in vulnerable conditions. In some Jain sites, the fragments of idols are found neglected by the roadsides which are also subjected to weathering, pollution and theft. It has been observed that Jain Antiquities are lied beneath a tree and the roots of trees are destroying these invaluable artifacts. It is noticed that in very few places, the fragmented idols are preserved in modern temples. Some artifacts collected from the study area are now preserved in district and state museums. On the basis of documentation provided in “Jainism in West Bengal: An Archaeological Approach”, compiled by Dr. S Majumdar, the present study attempted to classify Jain Antiquities in the study area into four types:

Figure 15. Classification of the Jain Heritage Sites (Source. Prepared by the Author)

- i) Abandoned Temples containing Jain Sculptures.
- ii) Jain Sculpture fragments beneath tree without any conservation effort.
- iii) Modern Temples preserving ancient Jain Sculptural remains.
- iv) Museums having collections of recovered Jain sculptural remains.

These four categories are symbolically distributed in figure 15.

Suggestions for Infrastructural Development for Better Tourism Experience in Jain Sites:

1. For the Government:

- 1.1) Improve the Conservation techniques and enhance the preservation initiatives.
- 1.2) Establish Government accommodations, sanitary facilities, drinking facilities, sitting arrangements, food court, book stalls, children's park, parking facilities around the important Jain sites like Bahulara, Sonatapol, Saileswar and Saeswar in Dihar, Dharapat etc.
- 1.3) Encourage local Souvenir shop owners at main hubs to keep souvenirs of Jain artifacts and crafts.
- 1.4) Install CCTV and security systems to prevent vandalism.
- 1.5) Install QR scanning code in each sites to provide related information with the Jain sites.
- 1.6) organize light and sound show in the Jain heritage sites.
- 1.7) Improve the road condition and install information board in each sites.
- 1.8) Arrange special facilities for the Jain Pilgrimage visitors.
- 1.9) Organize Jain heritage walks for the school students and tourists
- 1.10) Promote and support Jain studies or archaeological researches.

2. For the Local Community:

- 2.1) Be respectful to those sites which bears the evidence of this type of Glorious ideology.
- 2.2) Arrange 'Mahavir Jayanti', 'Chaturmasa', 'Paryushana', 'Akshaya Tertiya' etc. festivals in those sites.
- 2.3) Arrange local awareness campaign for promoting the historical and ideological significance of those sites.
- 2.4) Make interactions with Jain sponsor groups for financial support.

8. Conservation strategies by Local Community:

Local communities play a crucial role in the preservation and sustainability of Jain heritage sites, especially in rural areas where formal administrative monitoring is limited. Since many Jain antiquities in Bankura district are located in villages, agricultural fields, forest fringes, and roadside locations, the active involvement of local residents becomes indispensable for their long-term conservation. Community awareness regarding the historical, religious, and cultural significance of these sites can significantly reduce vandalism, neglect, and unintentional damage.

One of the most effective strategies is the organization of community-based awareness programs, heritage walks, and local workshops that educate villagers, students, and youth groups about the importance of Jain ideology and its archaeological legacy. Local schools, clubs, and cultural organizations can collaborate to promote heritage education through exhibitions, storytelling sessions, and celebration of Jain festivals such as *Mahavir Jayanti*, *Paryushana*, and *Chaturmasa* at or near the heritage sites. Such activities foster a sense of ownership and pride among the local population.

Additionally, local communities can assist in basic site maintenance, such as regular cleaning, protection of sculptures from vegetation overgrowth, and reporting cases of theft or damage to authorities. Village-level committees or heritage protection groups may be formed to monitor vulnerable sites. Collaboration with Jain trusts, philanthropic organizations, and NGOs can also provide financial and logistical support for minor conservation works. By integrating livelihood opportunities such as guiding services, souvenir production, and homestays, conservation efforts can be linked with local economic benefits, ensuring community-driven and sustainable heritage preservation.

9. Conservation Strategies by Central and State Archaeological Department:

The Central and State Archaeological Departments have a decisive role in safeguarding Jain heritage sites through scientific conservation, legal protection, and policy-level interventions. Many Jain sites in Bankura district remain either unprotected or insufficiently documented, making them highly vulnerable to natural weathering, encroachment, and illicit trafficking. Therefore, systematic documentation, mapping, and grading of Jain archaeological sites should be undertaken using modern geospatial tools, as demonstrated in the present study.

Priority should be given to declaring historically significant and vulnerable Jain temples and sculpture sites as protected monuments under the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) or the State Archaeology Department of West Bengal. Regular structural assessments, conservation treatments, and controlled excavation programs should be carried out by trained professionals following standard archaeological conservation protocols. The relocation of severely endangered movable artifacts to district or state museums may be considered where in-situ preservation is not feasible.

Furthermore, the departments should focus on infrastructure development and site interpretation, including the installation of informative signboards, QR-code-based digital interpretation systems, fencing, CCTV surveillance, and visitor amenities. Integration of Jain heritage sites into broader cultural tourism circuits, supported by improved road connectivity

and signage, can enhance visibility while ensuring controlled tourism. Capacity-building programs for local stakeholders, along with inter-departmental coordination between tourism, archaeology, and local governance bodies, will strengthen conservation outcomes and promote sustainable heritage tourism in the region.

10. Conclusion:

The present study highlights the immense but largely untapped potential of ancient Jain heritage sites in Bankura district as significant destinations for pilgrimage and cultural heritage tourism. By employing a geospatial approach, the research successfully mapped the spatial distribution, accessibility, connectivity, and conservation status of Jain archaeological sites, thereby offering a comprehensive framework for tourism planning and heritage management. The integration of GIS-based techniques such as circuit planning, isochrone mapping, buffer analysis, and road network density analysis provides valuable insights for both researchers and policymakers.

The findings reveal that although Bankura district possesses a rich assemblage of Jain temples, sculptures, and iconographic remains, many of these sites suffer from neglect, inadequate conservation, and limited tourism infrastructure. The study emphasizes that sustainable development of Jain heritage tourism cannot be achieved solely through government intervention; rather, it requires a synergistic approach involving local communities, archaeological authorities, tourism planners, and academic institutions.

In conclusion, the conservation and promotion of Jain heritage sites in Bankura district hold significant potential not only for preserving an invaluable chapter of India's religious and cultural history but also for fostering rural development and sustainable tourism. Strategic planning supported by geospatial technology, coupled with community participation and institutional commitment, can transform these neglected sites into vibrant centers of heritage tourism while ensuring their protection for future generations.

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